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Preregistering qualitative research

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Preregistering qualitative research

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ABSTRACT

The threat to reproducibility and awareness of current rates of research misbehavior sparked initiatives to better academic science. One initiative is preregistration of quantitative research. We investigate whether the preregistration format could also be used to boost the credibility of qualitative research. A crucial distinction underlying preregistration is that between *prediction* and *postdiction*. In qualitative research, data are used to decide which way interpretation should move forward, using data to generate hypotheses and new research questions. Qualitative research is thus a real-life example of postdiction research. Some may object to the idea of preregistering qualitative studies because qualitative research generally does not test hypotheses, and because qualitative research design is typically flexible and subjective. We rebut these objections, arguing that making hypotheses explicit is just one feature of preregistration, that flexibility can be tracked using preregistration, and that preregistration would provide a check on subjectivity. We then contextualize preregistrations alongside another initiative to enhance credibility in qualitative research: the confirmability audit. Besides, preregistering qualitative studies is practically useful to combating dissemination bias and could incentivize qualitative researchers to report constantly on their study's development. We conclude with suggested modifications to the Open Science Framework preregistration form to tailor it for qualitative studies.

KEYWORDS

Preregistration; qualitative research; transparency

Relevance

- Importance recognised by various *stakeholders*
- Qualitative preregistration *counterintuitive*
- Different authors put forth *ideas*; no *systematic empirical investigation*

Goal: to understand what *parts of preregistration* templates qualitative researchers would find *informative*

Delphi study

Consecutive *questionnaires* with *feedback* reports in between

Otherwise *dispersed* group, not one person that can *dominate*

Panelists

Fourfold strategy

1. **Own** network
2. Reporting **guidelines**
3. '**Active**' qualitative researchers
4. **Suggested** colleagues

Total: **294 invitees**

Creation questionnaire

Fourfold approach

1. Integrated *existing works*
2. Systematic search in *PubMed* and *PsycINFO*
3. Screened 21 reporting guidelines published on *EQUATOR*
4. Put forth this list of 36 proposals to *steering committee*

Result: **21** proposals

New Registration

Study Info

Design Plan

Data Collection

Analysis Plan

Design Plan

Study Type

Please describe your study type(s). Typical study types are case studies, evaluation research, intervention research, participatory research. In addition, if you do participatory research, you may want to elaborate on whether the participation is overt or covert.

Questions

1. Term
2. Elaboration
3. Relevance
4. Heading

To what extent do you agree with the suggested...?

Arguments!

Agreement criterion

≥68% -- “Strongly agree” **OR** “Somewhat agree”

Criterion was preregistered, see osf.io/en3qc

Results round 1

35 researchers completed questionnaire (response rate: 12%)

14 proposals relevant → merged into 11 ***revised proposals***

2 proposals had 66% and 65% scores & conflicting arguments → put forth ***again***

New Registration

Study Info

Design Plan

Data Collection

Analysis Plan

Design Plan

Study Design

Please indicate and describe your research design. Examples of study designs include phenomenology, ethnography, grounded theory, or case study. Your specific study design could be a combination of different research designs, or even both quantitative and qualitative methods.

Questions

To what extent do you agree with the suggested...?

1. **Revised** term
 - ? based on panel members' arguments
2. **Revised** elaboration
 - ? based on panel members' arguments

Arguments!

Results round 2

31 researchers completed questionnaire (response rate: 11%)

9 proposed terms >68% agreement → *slightly* revised

10 proposed elaborations >68% agreement → *slightly* revised

2 optional proposals → actually *relevant*

Figure 3. Visualization of the Delphi feedback process.

Outcome

Voluntarily, systematic ***starting-point***

Extra '***modules***'

Connection ***reporting guidelines***

No empirical evidence for ***rigour***

Integration

Register

Registration creates a frozen version of the project. Your original project remains editable.

Things to know about registration:

- Registrations cannot be edited or deleted.
- Withdrawing a registration removes its contents, but leaves behind basic metadata: title, contributors, date registered, date withdrawn, and justification (if provided).
- Registrations can be public or embargoed for up to four years. Embargoed registrations will be made public automatically when the embargo expires.

Continue your registration from the following form:

- OSF Preregistration
- Open-Ended Registration
- Qualitative Preregistration** ⓘ
- Registered Report Protocol Preregistration ⓘ
- OSF-Standard Pre-Data Collection Registration ⓘ
- Preregistration Template from AsPredicted.org ⓘ
- Replication Recipe (Brandt et al., 2013): Post-Completion ⓘ
- Replication Recipe (Brandt et al., 2013): Pre-Registration ⓘ
- Pre-Registration in Social Psychology (van 't Veer & Giner-Sorolla, 2016): Pre-Registration ⓘ

This template was created by researchers from the qualitative community for preregistration of qualitative research.

OSFHOME

My Projects Search Support Donate Tamarinde Haven

Search OSF

Enter search term(s) here

1833 results

Refine

Registration template: Qualitative Preregistration

REGISTRATION

Automatically analysed video interviews and ethnic minorities

Alex Bédard, Maura Burke, Sarah Douchal, Colleen O'Brien, Christine Uss, and 1 more

Barriers to qualitative preregistration?

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Whether preregistration is *useful* depends on one's
research paradigm

TABLE 6.1 Basic Beliefs (Metaphysics) of Alternative Inquiry Paradigms

<i>Item</i>	<i>Positivism</i>
Ontology	naive realism— “real” reality but apprehendable
Epistemology	dualist/objectivist; findings true

TABLE 6.1 Basic Beliefs (Metaphysics) of Alternative Inquiry Paradigms

<i>Item</i>	<i>Positivism</i>	<i>Postpositivism</i>	<i>Critical Theory et al.</i>	<i>Constructivism</i>
Ontology	naive realism— “real” reality but apprehendable	critical realism— “real” reality but only imperfectly and probabilistically apprehendable	historical realism— virtual reality shaped by social, political, cultural, economic, ethnic, and gender values; crystallized over time	relativism—local and specific constructed realities
Epistemology	dualist/objectivist; findings true	modified dualist/ objectivist; critical tradition/community; findings probably true	transactional/ subjectivist; value- mediated findings	transactional/ subjectivist; created findings

Uptake[★]

All Journals

TOP Standard ^

- Total TOP Factor
- Data Citation
- Data Transparency
- Analysis Code Transparency
- Materials Transparency
- Design & Analysis Reporting Guidelines
- Study Preregistration

Comprehensive Results in Social Psychology

3

Personality and Social Psychology Review

3

The Journal of Politics

3

Cortex

2

European Journal of Personality

2

Exceptional Children

2

Health Psychology

2

Journal of Applied Psychology

2

TOP Guidelines

Replication of Empirical Analysis: Acceptance is conditional on successful replication of empirical (quantitative or qualitative) analysis. For more information see “Instructions for Authors of Accepted Manuscripts” below.

The following items should be addressed in research manuscripts submitted to *Exceptional Children*:

- Authors must indicate whether the conducted research was preregistered with an analysis plan in an independent, institutional registry (e.g., <http://osf.io/>, <https://sreereg.icpsr.umich.edu/sreereg/>). What should be preregistered depends on study design. For group contrasts studies, preregistration involves registering the study design, variables, and treatment conditions. This includes an analysis plan including specification of sequence of analyses or the statistical model that will be reported.

Recommended preregistration components for qualitative and secondary data analyses can be found at the following website: <https://osf.io/zab38/wiki/home/>. Recommended guidelines for single-case

Uptake[★]

Research questions

Which aspects of the plans that were preregistered **are adjusted** in the final publication, and how are they modified?

Are these adjustments **explicitly justified**? If so, **how**?

Pilot

Design

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Descriptives by year

Used qual preregistration template

Preregistrations by Year (2020-2023)

Actual qualitative study

Qualitative (incl. review) preregistrations by year

Fields

Matching data

Analyses

Descriptive statistics

E.g., trends over time, disciplines, journals

Inductive content analysis

E.g., Parts changed, type of changes, justifications

Rigorous qualitative preregistration?

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Exploring examples

Example 1:

<https://osf.io/h5gmc>

Example 2:

<https://osf.io/byw9c>

Example 3:

<https://osf.io/rhn25>

Harvesting suggestions

Check the form and your criteria (on the blackboard)

Discuss with your group

One strength

One suggestion for improvement

What do you take away?

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